

SAPIENZA
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A Deep Learning Approach to EEG Subcortical Source Localization

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AEGEUS

A Novel EEG Ultrasound Device for Functional Brain Imaging and Neurostimulation

European
Innovation
Council

**Funded by
the European Union**

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Introduction

Objectives

Materials and Methods

Results

Conclusions

Future works

A prototype of the US transducers and imaging

Functional Ultrasound Imaging (fUS):

- Good coverage of deep structures
- Temporal resolution comparable to fMRI

A prototype of the US transducers and imaging

EEG topographic map

Electroencephalography:

- Lack of direct spatial localization
- Really high temporal resolution

AEGEUS

A prototype of the US transducers and imaging

EEG topographic map

Sensitivity to the cortex

Sensitivity to the hippocampi

AEGEUS

A prototype of the US transducers and imaging

EEG topographic map

Source Localization: Linear Inverse

EEG topographic map

Inferred electrical activity

Source Localization: Linear Inverse

EEG topographic map

Inferred electrical activity

Linear Inverse +
Spatial smoothing and averaging

$$\operatorname{argmin}_{\mathbf{J}} (\mathbf{L}\mathbf{J} - \mathbf{v})^T \mathbf{C}^{-1} (\mathbf{L}\mathbf{J} - \mathbf{v}) + \lambda^2 \mathbf{J}^T \mathbf{R}^{-1} \mathbf{J}$$

\mathbf{C} : Noise covariance matrix
 \mathbf{R} : Source covariance matrix
 \mathbf{L} : Leadfield matrix

Source Localization: Linear Inverse

EEG topographic map

v

Inferred electrical activity

J

Linear Inverse +
Spatial smoothing and averaging

$$\operatorname{argmin}_J (LJ - v)^T C^{-1} (LJ - v) + \lambda^2 J^T R^{-1} J$$

C : Noise covariance matrix
 R : Source covariance matrix
 L : Leadfield matrix

Selected methods:

- MNE
- MNE depthw
- LAURA
- dSPM
- dSPM depthw
- LORETA
- sLORETA
- sLORETA depthw
- eLORETA

Grech, R., Cassar, T., Muscat, J. et al. Review on solving the inverse problem in EEG source analysis.

Source Localization: Neural Networks

EEG topographic map

Inferred electrical activity

Neural Networks:

- High flexibility
- Promising results

R. Sun, A. Sohrabpour, G.A. Worrell, & B. He, Deep neural networks constrained by neural mass models improve electrophysiological source imaging of spatiotemporal brain dynamics

Objectives

- Improve deep EEG source localization with neural networks
 - Develop a simulation tool to evaluate localization
 - Define a neural network to perform source reconstruction
 - Evaluate improvements on state of the art methods

Simulations: Brain Activity

time=16.815s

Autoregressive simulator

Resting state

Increase + Synchronize

time=16.815s

Source activity

Patch generator

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Simulations: EEG

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Source activity

Forward Problem

Simulated EEG

Window at 50 samples

Prediction Problem

Activation Pattern

Simulations: EEG

time=16.815s

Source activity

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Activation Pattern

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Neural Network Architecture

0.2 s EEG recording

LSTM hidden unit

Dipole activations

- **LSTM** network
- Regression task
- Binary Cross-Entropy
- 140M parameters (~500 MB)

Performance Metrics

- **Localization Error (LE):** Distance between real and predicted center of activity.
- **DistRank:** Measures how far the algorithm is from correctly predicting the true center of activity.
- **$AUC_{close}^{[*]}$:** Measures how easily the boundary of the true region can be reconstructed.

Reconstruction with low LE

[*] C. Grova, J. Daunizeau, J.-M. Lina, C.G. Bénar, H. Benali, J. Gotman, Evaluation of EEG localization methods using realistic simulations of interictal spikes.

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Reconstruction with low DistRank

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Reconstruction with low AUC_{close}

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Representative Regions

-20 minutes recording (650 samples)

-The network is compared to the best performing classical method

Cortical Performances

	<i>LSTM</i>	<i>sLORETA</i>	<i>Perfect</i>
LE (mm)	9	5	0
AUC_{close}	0.987	0.949	1
DistRank	0.002	0.000	0

LSTM

sLORETA

	<i>LSTM</i>	<i>MNE</i>	<i>Perfect</i>
LE (mm)	10	14	0
AUC_{close}	0.995	0.920	1
DistRank	0.001	0.012	0

LSTM

MNE

Subcortical Performances

True

	<i>Perfect</i>	<i>LSTM</i>	<i>sLORETA depthw</i>
LE (mm)	0	3	16
AUC_{close}	1	0.998	0.903
DistRank	0	0.001	0.021

Subcortical Performances

True

LSTM

sLORETA

	<i>Perfect</i>	<i>LSTM</i>	<i>sLORETA</i>
LE (mm)	0	10	12
AUC_{close}	1	0.987	0.874
DistRank	0	0.005	0.015

Conclusions

- Results show that it is possible to identify the shape of the active region
- Classical methods can localize deep sources with **LE** < 2cm
- Our network consistently improves on classical methods, **LE** < 1cm, higher **AUC**_{close}

LSTM

sLORETA depthw

Future works

- Increase anatomical realism in simulations

- Evaluate the integration with ultrasound data from the AEGEUS project
- Test on clinical EEG from patients with deep seizure onset

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Thank you!

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